

REMEDIES FOR PSYCHOLOGICAL BARRIERS IN LISTENING IN ENGINEERING COLLEGES

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Education brings about changes in individual's social cognitive and psycho-motor domains. These changes take place in unisons and not in an isolated stage. The individual achieves knowledge and acquires the required skill. These changes are made possible by effective teaching and learning student development starts as soon as the student creates an interest and involvement in learning.

Learners are of many types.

- ✓ Visual Learners
- ✓ Auditory Learners
- ✓ Kinesthetic Learners
- ✓ Group Learners

Barriers of listening are of many types.

- ✓ Linguistic Barriers
- ✓ Physical Barriers
- ✓ Psychological Barriers
- ✓ Cultural Barriers

This paper focuses on analyzing the efficacy of listening skills. It is a well known fact that listening skills is the most important skill for the student. But they have a wrong notion that it need not be learnt. This is because of their assumption that it is a natural skill.

Psychological barrier results from the learner's disturbed state of mind. They are emotionally disturbed due to classroom environment, peer pressure, inferiority complex, discouragement from friends, lack of knowledge of the outer world, parental pressure etc. because of all these factors his focus on listening gets disturbed. Listening is the result of co operation of the mind while receiving the auditory information. Majority of the students have the average level of emotional intelligence. The students are in the period of community and nature of the college also can be taken as a reason for the psychological problem of a student.

The problem occurs due to the stress created by their parents also. It is a well known fact that the engineering degree which they were not able to study is thrust upon their children. The number of students joining in engineering colleges is increasing today. Some of the students who join in engineering colleges are first generation learners. Many students feel inferior as they come from vernacular medium.

A lot of problems could be attributed to the psychological problems that we find among the students. They focus on writing exams and pressure from all the sides to get high marks drive the student to madness and he is depressed. He develops a fear towards learning. This results in poor listening in the lecture delivered in the class. The student is also afraid of the teacher who sometimes mocks at him for his language skills. The student a mind to excel in the learning skills but his shyness is a hindrance for him. Many of the first generation learners have no guidance from the parents for acquiring language skills. At the tertiary level, students are assessed based on their performance in the summative assessments.

The process of listening and responding is complex. Most teachers allow little time for responding to them. Due to this the students who know the answer is not able to answer the teacher. This disturbs them a lot. Some students switch off under their pressure. They give the answer to themselves not knowing whether it is right or wrong. The limited knowledge of vocabulary also makes the students dull as they are not able to understand the message of the speaker. Here their self confidence level goes down. They are unable to share their problems to anyone. They are helpless. They are unable to comprehend an expanded range of concrete, abstract and conceptual language. A psychological barrier is a limiting benefit that prevents a person from reaching his full potential.

Feelings of anger, sadness, ecstasy, emotional attachments with other students and poor economical background may severely disturb a listener's ability.

Listening is undoubtedly a psychological phenomenon. Mental disturbance leads to distraction in listening. Valuable information is missed if there is a lack of attention in listening.

The unwavering determination of the teachers to deal with a student who has poor listening skill will prove useful. They should ensure that the listener is in a normal state of mind in the classroom. Some teachers have a mindset that the students with psychological disorders are non-achievers. The teachers can ask the other students of the class not to bully or tease these students. Appreciation and encouragement from the teacher

boosts their learning skill. In turn they are attentive in the class. The teachers should counsel the students with drug-related problems. Even if the teacher is unable to identify the psychological problem she can create a friendly atmosphere and rectify the problem. The student may not be aware of his appropriate behavior. If the teacher suspects that a student has a psychological problem, he can advice the student advice the student about his behavior. The teacher can take it as a challenge and balance between respecting the limits of his position and dealing with the students.

The teacher should actively listen to a student when he shares his problems. Low self esteem, anxiety are also some of the reasons for the poor listening of the students. The teacher can politely and non-intrusively check back some days later about the improvement in the listening skill of the students. Many playway methods and tasks also help the students come out of their psychological problems and get involved in the classroom.

To conclude the teacher should make the students realize that there is a change possible if they come out of the psychological problems. A holistic approach can help the teachers to make the students break the psychological barrier and acquire listening skills which is the need of the hour.

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